

Synthesis, characterization of a new tamarind based ion exchange resin and use for the separation of heavy metal ions in industrial wastewater

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Abstract : A new tamarind kernel powder based resin containing 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid group has been synthesized by modified Porath's method of functionalisation of polysaccharides. Resin synthesized from TKP possesses an excellent ion-exchange property due to high selectivity for metal ions. The resin was characterized on the basis of chemical composition, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, ion-exchange capacity, thermogravimetric analysis and physicochemical properties. The distribution coefficient (K_d) values and influence of pH on chelation of these metal ions were studied using batch method. The separations of mixture of Fe^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} metal ions on TND SA resin on the basis of their distribution coefficient at various pH were also achieved using column chromatograph. The effects of experimental parameters such as pH, treatment time, temperature and resin dose on the removal of metal ions have been also studied. These results show that TND SA resin hold great potential to remove heavy metal species from industrial wastewater.

Keywords : Ion exchange capacity, TND SA resin, batch method, distribution coefficient, heavy metal ions.

Introduction

An excess amount of heavy metal ions in aquatic environments is known to cause severe damage to human health and aquatic life. Therefore, separation of these metal ions in natural water at trace level is of paramount importance both for water purification and analysis. The complete removal of heavy toxic metal ions that is incompatible with the biological system requires expensive treatment to turn again useful as domestic waters¹. It is essential to extend methods for removal of metal ions to decrease the pollution load on the environment. Various methods have been developed for the removal of these metal ions from aqueous systems such as solvent extraction², precipitation and coprecipitation³, electrochemical reduction⁴, chemical and bio sorption⁵, preconcentration⁶, reverse osmosis⁷ and ion exchange⁸⁻¹¹. In recent years, the adsorption process has also received much attention and becomes one of the more popular methods for the removal of heavy metal ions from the wastewater because of its competitive and effective process. Though numerous adsorbents have been reported for the removal of toxic metal ions, such as chitin¹², chitosan¹³, starch¹⁴,

cellulose¹⁵⁻¹⁹, guaran²⁰, cyclodextrin²¹ which are not only eco-friendly and cost-effective but are effective also in remediation of common effluents present in the wastewater. Other polysaccharide based materials and aluminosilicates are used as adsorbent in wastewater treatment²²⁻²⁴. Adsorption using commercial activated carbon (CAC) can remove metal ions from waste water, such as Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cr^{II} and Cu^{II}²⁵⁻²⁸. Resins prepared with divinylbenzene-styrene backbone and petrochemicals are hydrophobic and costly²⁹. Their ion exchange capacity depends mainly on the quantity of functional groups and the pH of the solution. The most widespread chelating functional groups used for removal of metal ions from effluents are thiol³⁰, thiourea³¹, dithizone³², aspartate and triisobutyl phosphine sulfide³⁴.

Industrial effluents are one of the main pollution factors due to metal industries and derivatives. Therefore, ion exchange treatment seems to be preferred to other processes. Many literature data have been reported for the removal of toxic metal ions from industrial effluent. Singh *et al.* studied the synthesis of tamarind imminodiacetic acid (TIDAA) cation exchanger and its

application in removal of aguncha open cast mine, Bhilwara Rajasthan, India²⁰. Samarkandy *et al.* studied the synthesis and development of novel aminated chelating resin and its application in industrial waste water treatment³⁵. Singh *et al.* studied the synthesis and characterization of tamarind anthranilic acid (TAA) resin and its use in removal of toxic metal ions from effluent of Jackson Paint Industry, Jodhpur, India³⁶.

Tamarind kernel powder (TKP) is obtained from the seeds of the tamarind tree, *Tamarindus indica*, a common forest and cultivated tree found primarily in India, Burma, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka. TKP is a polymer with an average molecular weight of 52350 and a monomer contains three sugars glucose, galactose, and xylose in a molar ratio of 3 : 1 : 2, as reported by Khanna³⁷. About 80% of the glucose residues are substituted by a 1+6 linked xylose units, which themselves are partially substituted by 1-2 galactose residues³⁸. The structure of TKP is given in Fig. 1.

The ion exchangers based on tamarind kernel powder is hydrophilic and biodegradable, whereas ion exchangers prepared from petrochemical product are hydrophobic and not biodegradable. Due to rising prices of petroleum products TKP has been selected for development of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA) resin. Its cost is low, it is locally available in large quantities

from agricultural resources and such biopolymers are eco-friendly.

Present work was undertaken to study the synthesis and characterization of TNDSA resin and its applications for removal and recovery of toxic metal ions from effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India in the form of batch and column processes. Various factors affecting adsorption conditions, pH, temperature, treatment time and resin dose on the removal of metal ions have been studied.

Results and discussion

(a) *Characterization of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA) resin :*

FT-IR characterization of (TNDSA) resin :

Varian model 640 FTIR instrument was employed for the FTIR spectral analysis of synthesized TNDSA resin using KBr pellets. The types of vibration and absorption ranges (cm^{-1}) in TNDSA resin is given in Table 1 and full agreement with published results³⁹.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

For this purpose 951 thermogravimetric analyzer was employed. The TNDSA resin is found to stable up to 405 °C and then the degradation was found to be rapid. The results of the TGA are given in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Average primary structure of tamarind seed polysaccharide. The cellulose type backbone is substituted by xylose (a 1-6) and galactose (8 1-c2) xylose (cu 1-6) residues.

Table 1. FT-IR characterization of TNDSA resin

Type of vibration	Absorption ranges (cm ⁻¹)
C-C-H stretching vibrations	3000-2900
C=C-H stretching	3100-3000
C-H bending	1480-1350
O-H stretching	3600-3200
O-H bending	1650
C-O stretching	1300-1000
C=C stretching (In aromatic nuclei)	1620-1450
S=O stretching (Asymmetric and symmetric)	1350-1340 and 1165-1150

Table 2. Physico-chemical characteristics of the synthesized tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid resin

Property	Value (SD)
Active group	-SO ₃ H
Ionic form as a shipped	H ⁺
% Moisture	15.6 ± 0.5
% Solid	84.4 ± 0.5
True density (g/cm ³)	1.41 ± 0.02
Apparent density (g/ml)	0.6568 ± 0.0056
Void volume fraction	0.3592 ± 0.1168
Volume capacity (mmol/cm ³)	2.96 ± 0.05
Total exchange capacity (meq/g)	3.18 ± 0.05
Particle size (mm)	0.30 ± 0.05
Thermal stability	405°
Operating pH range	1-7
Elemental analysis	C = 43.28 (theor. : 43.46) H = 5.11 (theor. : 5.18) O = 45.98 (theor. : 46.09)

Elemental analysis :

Carlo Erba model 1160 elemental analyzer (CHO) was used for determination of percentage of elements in the synthesized resin. The results are given in Table 2.

(b) Discussions on distribution coefficient (K_d) values :

Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions in reference solution and effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur :

The pH of experimental solution has a strong effect on the distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions. Tables 3 and 4 shows that the variation of K_d values of different metal ions with (H⁺), which reveals the increase of the K_d values (reference solution and effluent) with decreasing acidity of the aqueous solution and optimum results

Table 3. Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from reference solution on TNDSA resin

pH	Amount of resin used = 0.1 g				
	Zn ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Pb ²⁺
1	1306	3566	2891	1092	1294
2	3394	8346	8434	1865	2106
3	9246	17868	15667	2509	3587
4	25882	10429	10696	4155	6463
5	13357	4155	4602	7621	10628
6	4118	2106	2150	11658	4076
7	1842	1280	1342	2650	1519

obtained at pH range 3-6. Metal sorption starts when the pH rises to the range where most acidic ion exchange sites start to exchange hydronium ion for metal and the capacity reaches the maximum value in the pH range where all the ion exchange sites take part in the reaction and the functional group is able to form complex with the metal cations⁴⁰. The presence of anions does not effect on the determination of K_d values.

Effect of pH :

The pH is an important parameter for adsorption of metal ions from aqueous solution because it affects the solubility of the metal ions, concentration of the counter ions on the functional groups of the adsorbent and the degree of ionization of the adsorbent during reaction. To examine the adsorption percentage of metal ions with pH, the pH was varied from 1.0 to 7.0 as given in Table 4. The uptake of free metal ions depends on pH, where optimum adsorption of metal ions occurs at different pH (3 to 6) and then declining at higher pH. At lower pH (acidic pH), the adsorbent surface will be completely covered with hydronium ions which compete strongly with metal ions for adsorption sites. With an increase in pH, the concentration of H₃O⁺ ions decreases, facilitating the adsorption of metal ions by the adsorbent⁴¹.

Effect of treatment time :

Treatment time indicate that adsorption percentage of metal ions increased with an increase in contact time before equilibrium is reached. Adsorption of metal ions on TNDSA resin increased when contact time was increased from 30 to 210 min, optimum contact time for TNDSA adsorbent was found to be 210 min. Other parameters such as pH of solution and agitation speed were kept optimum, while temperature was kept at 25 °C. Greater

Table 4. Distribution coefficient (K_d) and removal percentage of metal ions from effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur on TNSDA resin

pH	Amount of resin used = 0.1 g									
	Zn^{2+}		Fe^{2+}		Cu^{2+}		Cd^{2+}		Pb^{2+}	
	K_d	Removal (%)	K_d	Removal (%)	K_d	Removal (%)	K_d	Removal (%)	K_d	Removal (%)
1	922	47.97	2482	71.28	710	41.51	680	40.49	836	45.53
2	2824	73.85	6222	86.15	1184	54.20	1157	53.64	1701	62.98
3	7931	88.80	13857	93.27	2750	73.33	1948	66.08	3123	75.74
4	19893	95.21	9470	90.44	6200	86.11	3303	76.76	5528	84.68
5	9241	90.24	3771	79.04	11857	92.22	6282	86.26	9106	90.00
6	3561	78.08	1722	63.26	3809	79.21	10065	90.96	3312	76.80
7	1014	50.34	945	48.59	1154	53.57	3057	75.35	1410	58.51

availability of sulphonic acid and ether functional groups on the surface of TKP which are required for interaction with metal ions, significantly improved the binding capacity and the process proceeded rapidly.

Effect of treatment temperature :

The effect of treatment temperature on the adsorption percentage of the metal ions on TNSDA resin shows that the adsorption percentage of metal ions decreases by increasing the treatment temperature from 25 to 50 °C and than to 75 °C at optimum treatment time of 4 h. The working capacity of an ion exchanger depends on metal concentrations and temperatures. This observation is in full agreement with the published work⁴².

(c) Application of TNSDA resin :

Removal of metal ions from effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur by TNSDA resin :

The results of percentage removal of metal ions from effluent of Paradise Steel Industry by TNSDA resin are summarized in Table 4. The adsorption percentage of the metal ions on the TNSDA resin increases with pH and reaches its maximum value at pH range 3–6 and then declining at higher pH. This is at per with the trend in K_d values (Table 4). The relative standard deviation values (RSD) of optimum removal percentage of metal ions in effluent are shown in Table 5. It is clear from the reported table that the percentage removal of metal ions first increases and then decreases with increasing pH. The similar results obtained with previous study with Amberlite IR-120⁴³. It suggests that selectivity of metal ion is dependent on pH. The maximum removal of toxic metal ions have obtained, when strong electric field are

present and electrostatic effect may become the dominant factor, such that small ions, which have a huge charge density are bound more strongly with resin⁴⁴. In acidic medium, the H^+ ion of TNSDA resin easily exchange with metal ions.

Use of eluent and recovery of metal ions in industrial effluent :

The recovery of adsorbed metal ions were obtained by column experiment. In the column experiment the metal ions were eluted quantitatively with different strength of acids. The Pb^{II} was eluted with 0.1 N HCl, Cd^{II} with 0.5 N HCl, Cu^{II} with 1.0 N HCl, Fe^{II} with 1.5 N HCl and Zn^{II} was eluted with 2.0 N HCl. Then the resin column was washed thoroughly with demineralized water. The amounts of metal ions in the filtrate solution were analyzed by using AAS. Recovery of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} and Zn^{II} were obtained 94.28, 95.22, 95.52, 96.08 and 98.25% respectively. The elution of metal ions were carried out with hydrochloric acid solution taken the advan-

Table 5. Optimum results for the removal of metal ions from the effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur on TNSDA resin

Metal ions	Amount of resin used = 0.1 g			
	Amount of metal ions in effluent (mg)	Amount adsorbed on TNSDA resin (mg)	Removal ^a (%)	RSD (%)
Zn^{2+}	4.68	4.456	95.21	1.78
Fe^{2+}	1.56	1.455	93.27	1.42
Cu^{2+}	1.26	1.162	92.22	1.65
Cd^{2+}	0.852	0.775	90.96	2.32
Pb^{2+}	0.47	0.423	90.00	2.65

^aResult of triplicate analysis.

tage that, chloride ion is an acceptable matrix for both AAS and spectrophotometric determination of metal ion. Data obtained in Table 6 indicated that, different quantity and different strength of hydrochloric acid solution could afford quantitative elution of different metal ions from the resin. Dev and Rao have used modified Amberlite XAD-4 with bis-(*N,N*-salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine for the separation of Ni^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} and sorbed metals were eluted by 1 M HCl with a recovery of 98–100%⁴⁵. Literature data have been reported that the Pb^{II} was eluted with 0.02–1 N HCl at pH 6.0 and recovery was about 96%⁴⁶.

Table 6. Quantitative separation of metal ions on TNDSA column

Metal ions	Amount loaded (mg)	Amount found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Eluent use (N HCl)	Eluent volume (ml)
Zn ²⁺	4.456	4.378	98.25	2.0	60
Fe ²⁺	1.455	1.398	96.08	1.5	55
Cu ²⁺	1.162	1.112	95.52	1.0	50
Cd ²⁺	0.775	0.738	95.22	0.5	45
Pb ²⁺	0.425	0.402	94.58	0.1	45

Column reusability :

To test the long-term stability of the column containing the TNDSA resin, it was subjected to successive adsorption and desorption cycles by passing a metal ion solution through it at the optimum flow rate. The sorbed metal ion is then desorbed from the resin by appropriate eluent. The procedure was carried out several times. The stability of the column was assessed by monitoring the change in the recoveries of the sorbed metal ions. Results of ten adsorption/desorption cycles in Table 7 indicated that, the recovery decreased by 1–2% for metal ions, which reflect the good stability of the organic ligand on

Table 7. The recovery percentage of different metal ions on TNDSA resin (adsorption and desorption)

Metal ions	Recovery percentage of different metal ions onto TNDSA resin after cycles				
	1	2	4	8	10
Zn ²⁺	95.21	92.31	90.13	90.08	90.07
Fe ²⁺	93.27	90.28	88.32	88.31	88.31
Cu ²⁺	92.22	89.36	87.18	87.17	87.16
Cd ²⁺	90.96	87.91	85.88	85.86	85.85
Pb ²⁺	90.00	87.13	85.08	85.07	85.06

the resin.

Effect of TNDSA dose on adsorption of metal ions :

The resin amount is also important parameters to obtain the quantitative adsorption of metal ions. Amount of the resin were tested in the range of 20–200 mg and equilibrated for 4 h. It is apparent that by increasing the resin amount, the adsorption density, and the amount adsorbed metal ions per unit mass increases. The maximum adsorption by TNDSA resin was achieved with an adsorbent dose of 100 mg and continued decreasing up to 200 mg. The initial increase adsorption percentage of metal ions was due to the availability of more surface area and adsorption sites⁴⁷.

Experimental

Chemicals and sample :

The chemical used in the present work were e.g. TKP (Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India), epichlorohydrin (Loba Chemic Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India), 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (Loba Chemic Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India), sodium hydroxide (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, Baroda, India), dioxane (E. Merck, Mumbai, India). The reference solution (self-made) first made 1000 mg L⁻¹ solution of metal ions (CuSO₄·5H₂O, (NH₄)₂Fe(SO₄)₂·6H₂O, CdSO₄·H₂O, Pb(NO₃)₂, ZnSO₄·7H₂O, Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India) then dilute this solution contains Fe³⁺ (2 ppm), Cu²⁺ (2 ppm), Zn²⁺ (5 ppm), Cd²⁺ (1 ppm) and Pb²⁺ (1 ppm). The effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur (Rajasthan) has following characteristic features as given in Table 8.

Synthesis of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA) resin :

Synthesis of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid resin was accomplished in the following two steps, A and B.

(A) Preparation of epoxypropyl ether of tamarind :

An amount of 182.2 g of tamarind powder (0.2 mole) was taken in a round bottom flask and it was slurred with dioxane. Subsequently, 15 ml of 40% (w/v) sodium hydroxide was added to make alkaline, till pH reached 8.5 and the solution was stirred at 60 °C. Then 9.25 g (0.1 mole) epoxychloropropane (epichlorohydrin) was added with constant stirring. The stirring was further continued for 5 h at 60 °C. The product epoxypropyl ether

Table 8. The characteristic features of reference solution and effluent of Paradise Steel Industry, Jodhpur

Appearance	: Turbid						
Colour	: Dirty brown						
pH	: 5.6						
Total hardness	: 876 ppm						
Metal ion	Fe ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
Concentration (ppm)	1.56	1.26	4.68	0.47	0.85	129.6	198.2
Other anions (ppm) : fluoride = 0.86; sulphate = 487; cyanide = 0.03.							

of tamarind was filtered under vacuum and washed with methanol to remove impurities and dried.

(B) Preparation of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA) resin :

Epoxypropyl ether of tamarind synthesized in step A, was allowed to react with an amount of 30.4 g (0.1 mole) of 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid with stirring for 5 h at 60 °C and left overnight. The product was filtered under vacuum and washed with 90% methanol, containing few drops of hydrochloric acid to remove any inorganic impurities. Finally it was washed with pure methanol. The product tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA) resin was free flowing light yellow powder and yield was 221.3 g. The reaction scheme is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Synthesis of tamarind 1-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (TNDSA).

Water washing of ion-exchange resin :

The resins were washed with diluted HCl and then, the hydrogen form of the resin was washed with double distilled water to remove all the excess acid. The dried material at 378 K was used for further experimental work.

Physical and chemical characteristics :

The physico-chemical properties like percentage moisture content, percentage solid, true density, apparent density, void volume fraction and volume capacity and ion exchange capacity were studied according to standard methods^{48,49} and are summarized in Table 2.

Column experiment :

In the column experiment, a glass tube with 1.6 cm internal diameter and 20 cm height, packed with 8 cm of resin (7.5 g) was used. 50 ml of the sample metal ion solution were passed through the column at a flow rate of 2 ml per min. The flow rate was controlled by a peristaltic pump. The column was washed with 20 ml of deionized water and the washing was rejected. The metal ions were eluted quantitatively with different strength of acids.

Batch adsorption method :

A sample solution (100 ml) containing a known concentration of the studied metal ion were transferred to a Erlenmeyer flask and after adjusting its pH (by suitable buffer solution) values, 100 mg of the modified TNDSA resin was added to the solution and the mixture was shaken continuously in a temperature controlled shaker at 25 ± 2 °C for 4 h and the contents were equilibrated. The solution was filtered and metal ion concentration in the filtrate as well as in the residue was estimated using AAS. The K_d and percentage adsorption of the metal ions on TNDSA resin were calculated using the equations,

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion in resin phase}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution phase}} \times \frac{V}{m} \text{ ml g}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume of the solution (ml) and m is the weight of the dry resin (g) and

Percentage adsorption of metal ions =

$$\frac{C_i - C_f}{C_f} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where C_i is the initial concentration of metal ion in solution and C_f is the final amount of metal ion in solution after equilibrium with resin.

Conclusions :

The removal of Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions by TNDSA resin is now considered one of the most promising techniques due to its eco-friendliness, and rapidness. Some resins prepared with divinylbenzene-styrene backbone and petrochemicals are hydrophobic, costly and not eco-friendly²⁹. The optimum conditions for removal of Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions using TNDSA cation exchange resin were found to be pH range 3–6 and stirring time ~25 min. A concentration of 0.1–2.00 N HCl as eluent was sufficient to obtain maximum recovery for all metal ions from the obtained results. The relative standard deviations (RSD) of the repeatability and the reproducibility were < 3.0%. These results indicate that the present method can be used for quantitative analyses and removal of toxic metal ions. Exchange bed could be used more than 10 cycles with little loss of exchange capacity. The selectivity and ion-exchange capacity of these materials towards metals ions can be controlled by pH of the medium, resin dose, contact time and temperature etc. Therefore the TNDSA resin is applicable for the removal and recovery of heavy metal ions from industrial effluent.

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